

To Be a Gifted Adolescent

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Abstract: *Adolescence is a period in everybody's life that is usually referred to as "time that everybody must go through" or "parents' hell". Transition between childhood and adulthood is indeed of great importance in everybody's life, but it is usually accompanied with a variety of questions, problems, dilemmas and a constant need to choose among many possibilities, which adds a lot of tension to the adolescent's life and that of his or her family. Being gifted is also somewhat conflictual as it means – in most cases – a high cognitive level with somewhat lesser emotional development, along with many intellectual and educational needs that are hard to fulfil, and also usually difficult in finding peers with similar interests, level of thinking and verbal and/or logical-mathematical abilities. As a result, parents of gifted adolescents have to overcome the problems every parent of a teenager faces, and in addition – those caused by their children's giftedness. This work will open a window to many such issues not answered by education or mental health professionals. The problems presented in this part of my work are: Problems typical to adolescents; and Problems typical to the gifted with a special focus on their variations during adolescence. The second part of this article will deal with problems of gifted adolescents, namely – problems that usually do not occur among the non-gifted. In addition, I am to offer some effective ways and strategies that might help parents to deal with the challenge of raising a gifted adolescent.*

Keywords: Giftedness; adolescents; gifted; cognitive and emotional development; abilities; health; non-gifted.

To be a gifted adolescent: On children / Jubran Khalil Jubran

*Your children are not your children.
 They are the sons and daughters of Life's longing for itself.
 They come through you but not from you,
 And though they are with you yet they belong not to you.
 You may give them your love but not your thoughts,
 For they have their own thoughts.
 You may house their bodies but not their souls,
 For their souls dwell in the house of tomorrow,
 which you cannot visit, not even in your dreams.*

*You may strive to be like them, but seek not to make them like you.
 For life goes not backward nor tarries with yesterday.
 You are the bows from which your children as living arrows are sent forth.
 The archer sees the mark upon the path of the infinite,
 and He bends you with His might that His arrows may go swift and far.
 Let your bending in the archer's hand be for gladness;
 For even as He loves the arrow that flies, so He loves also the bow that is stable.*

Translated by Jubran Khalil Jubran

Introduction

The title: to be a gifted adolescent seems to be clear, simple, and by no means ambiguous. However, of the five words it contains only the three: “to be a” are clear, while both “adolescent” and “gifted” are quite intriguing. An “adolescent” has been defined in the second half of the 20th century substantially different than at the end of the nineteenth century; in the fifties it had a different meaning than in the eighties, and today it does not refer to what it was defined in 2000, less than a generation ago. Furthermore, parents have experienced their own adolescence as completely different from that of their children. Ongoing studies on adolescence, which started more than 100 years ago, with the publication of the monumental book by Hall (2008 [1904]) indicate that everything about adolescence, from the chronological delimitation, namely, at what age adolescence starts and when it ends, to the juristic, familial, social and educational meanings of adolescence is undefined, even fluid, depends on the geographical location, the specific social and familial culture, the religion and the level of religiosity, as well as on the gender, the educational agenda, the preferred psychological theory, etc.

In this work, adolescence will be referred at without being specific about the exact ages we are discussing. This vagueness will allow us to include a wide common ground as to the conflicts and problems adolescents and their parents typically deal with. However, it will not include ALL problems a gifted adolescent might have (David, 2017), but rather the ones occurring most often. Parents of gifted adolescents have to overcome the problems every parent of a teenager faces, and in addition – those caused by their children’s giftedness. This work will open a window to many such issues not answered by education or mental health professionals.

In addition to the familial components of each adolescent, there are external factors typical to each society, religion, and country – all of which are either enhancing or have the potential of harming the adolescent’s emotional stability. Only when the adolescent is strong enough mentally he or she is ready to face the challenges of adulthood. As Renati et al. (2016) summarize, without a healthy environment a child or an adolescent might adopt behavioral patterns and strategies that might damage their physical, social and emotional wellbeing. The problems I am presenting in this study are divided into three categories: however, only “two”

problems belonging to the first two categories will be discussed in this study. The third category of problem will be extensively discussed in the second part of my study.

1. Problems typical to adolescents;
2. Problems typical to the gifted with a special focus on their variations during adolescence;
3. Problems of gifted adolescents, namely – problems that usually do not occur among the non-gifted. (This part will be discussed in the next paper)

In addition, I am to offer some effective ways and strategies that might help parents to deal with the challenge of raising a gifted adolescent.

Discussing the problems typical to adolescents – with a focus on the gifted

Risk-taking with a focus on gifted adolescents can be divided into two types: Acts forbidden by law, such as drinking, cigarette smoking and drug taking, and those permitted by law, as motorcycling or sleeping outdoors (Crone & Dahl, 2012; Steinberg, 2007, 2008a); *sensation seeking* (Hoyle et al., 2002), and acting *impulsively* (Steinberg et al., 2008). There are many biological and physiological explanations to the increase in risk-taking, such as those given by Galvan et al. (2006, 2007); Gardner & Steinberg (2005) have given sociological explanations to this phenomenon. There are also biological, physiological and bio-chemical reasons to the increase in need of excitements during adolescence. Arnett (2006) claims that if an adolescent who needs excitement will not find an intellectual or moral interest he very well might find it in sex or drinking.

The need of a lot of sleep is typical to adolescent and vital to them (National Sleep Foundation, 2017) while *resisting to give up extra activities that require more waking hours*. As Carskadon (2012) has shown, this contradiction is a result of biological, psychological and social-cultural influences. It might cause the following:

1. The ability to learn, concentrate and solve problems is compromised. Even remembering important data, such as names, numbers, scheduled tasks or school tasks might be influenced;
2. Lack of sleep increases the risk of acne and other skin conditions;
3. Lack of sleep might contribute to aggressive or improper behavior, such as yelling at friends, or being impatient towards teachers or family members;
4. Lack of sleep often causes over- or unhealthy eating such as sweets resulting in over-weight;
5. Lack of sleep increases the influence of alcohol and probably also the need of caffeine and nicotine;
6. Lack of sleep contributes to the appearance of diseases, as well as to underuse of security means in general and while driving in particular.

Home tasks or the tasks of the adolescent and the disputes around them. Adolescents are able, in most cases, to take a part in all home tasks. The web of the American Academy of Pediatrics (2017) includes, among such tasks, arranging the adolescent's own belongings, washing her or his cloths, folding them and putting them into their drawers/closets, dust cleansing and sweeping, arranging the table for family meals, clearing the table after meals, dishwashing and putting the kitchenware back into their place, feeding the pets and taking them out, cleaning the birds' cages and their garbage cans, floor rinsing, sink-, toilet-, and bath-scrubbing; food preparing for school, cook dinner once a week, take care of the home yard and wash the family car. Actually, as we very well know, many families struggle when trying to make their adolescent children do even a minimal number of tasks, and quite often fail.

The adolescent's physical shape becomes a major issue, and many a time influences the life of the whole family. Among boys the most important components that are parts of the appearance are mainly height and muscularity; thus adolescent boys might pay too much attention to body building and to height comparisons with peers who are physically more developed. Among girls the two main physical issues are facial beauty and weight. The literature dealing with this subject is enormous; a google search of "adolescent, boys, girls, beauty, weight, height, muscular" gives 14,000,000 results; adding "journal article" gives a result of "only" 5,110,000 items. It can thus be argued that physical shape serves as a "business card" for adolescents, and as a result adolescents, especially girls, are substantially punished socially if they "don't care" about their looks. As much as adults try to "explain" adolescent girls that "there are more important things than being slim" parents, educators and professionals must take into consideration that many adolescents are not strong enough to pay the price of fighting against conventions regarding their looks. The only two possibilities they believe are "out there" are to conform to the social standards of beauty and thinness or to be an outsider, unpopular, a loner.

The need to belong to a group is very strong during adolescence (Randell et al., 2016; Rich Harris, 2009). This need is multi-faced: sometimes the adolescent adopts a behavior that is suitable to the society she or he belongs to. For example: the use of vulgar, rough languages, make deliberate syntax mistakes, use a lot of slang or cursing; sometimes the adolescent dresses "like everybody", a decision not accepted by the parents when it means torn cloths, very short skirts, or a cleavage considered too deep by the parents' criteria.

Choosing friends that the parents do not like. Sometimes one of the reasons an adolescent chooses a certain friend is because they think it will cause parental objection. Indeed, it is an unavoidable fact that many parents of adolescents do not like their child's friends. When an adolescent boy goes out with someone he knows his parents will not approve he is demonstrating his independence, a necessary step towards becoming a man. A boy should rebel against his parents' values, standards, aspirations and especially their preferences in order to grow up (Rich Harris, 2009). Parents that do not understand it will encounter a stronger resistance and eventually an irreversible disconnection with their children.

Parents' involvement in learning such as doing homework, preparing for examinations, paper writing. This involvement starts, many a time, in childhood, and often continues when the adolescent is used to the fact that her or his parents are responsible of their school assignments. Sometimes the adolescent wishes to stop this parental interference while the parents would not let go.

Parents who become drivers, servants, or social secretaries. Driving one's child or making appointments for her or him start, in most cases, while the child is still young. However, when this behavior pattern continuous when the child can use public transportation or just walk rather than be driven, or years after he or she has learnt how to use the telephone for a variety of social tasks, it might cause severe conflicts. *For example: the conflict between "I am not going to put your dirty underwear into the laundry basket" and "you cannot live in a room where there is a 2-week old pile of dirty laundry", or "I am tired of reminding you it is time to leave for your 5 o'clock basketball training" and "I have to help you be ready on time so that you are not late and eventually will be kicked out of the team".*

Restricting the home coming time. This issue consists of the questions what is the "right" time an adolescent should be home during week days and weekends as well as holidays and school vacations. These questions are of high importance as parents must adopt a fair, logical, rules system. For example: parents claim that they do not wish to be their child's drivers, but at the same time do not allow their adolescent daughter or son to get back home late saying: "you cannot come home at midnight". It also raises the gender issue, namely, should there be a different between adolescent boys and girls?

Taking part in family events. As the adolescent grows up, she or he becomes busier and less willing to participate in family dinners, family walks, tours, or journeys. This might cause increasing family disputes. Fixed rules have to be established as soon as possible, and all children must obey to them. There is no question of "what is right" but rather "what is right for our family", a question only the parents can answer.

Discussing the problems which are crucial to gifted adolescents but are common to non-gifted

Dealing with philosophical issues and asking existential questions. For example: does God exists? What happens after death? Why should we obey to social rules? To ethical rules? Such questions are typical to all adolescents, but they are asked more often by gifted adolescents, and the fact that they do not have one, absolute answer might cause more difficulties to gifted adolescents than to non-gifted teenagers (Webb et al., 2007).

High level of emotional sensitivity. Adolescence is, in general, a sensitive time (Arnett, 1999, 2006; Casey et al., 2010; Hall, 1904, Silvers et al., 2012). Sensitivity is also a characteristic of giftedness (Miller, 1996). As the two kinds of sensitivity – to others' moods, feelings, temperaments, and motivations (Gardner, 1993) and towards oneself – have introspective and self-reflective capacities, are considered two of the seven multi-intelligences, are considered

born-capacities, it can be assumed that the sensitivity level of the adolescent will get higher in time.

As to the issue of the consequences of this sensitivity there are a few assumptions. Kaplan (1990) claims that heightened sensitivity might result in high expectations to success, whether from myself or from others. The pressure put on the gifted adolescent increases and she or he is vulnerable to doubts about their abilities, and a constant feeling of lack of energy when the standards of success seem unreachable.

Problems related to over-excitation or hyper-sensitivity of at least one sense are very common among the gifted (Daniels, 2009; Daniels, & Piechowski, 2008; Daniels, & Meckstroth, 2008; David, 2009; Piechowski, 2006). During adolescence, while the social “rules” about clothing, that might not suit individuals with over-sensitivity to touch; about the use of various smells – such as deodorant, perfume or after-shave, that might be disturbing to individuals with hyper-sensitivity to smells, and especially to individuals who are expected to participate in noisy social events while suffering from hyper-sensitivity to noise, all these problems might become severe.

Parental authority and setting boundaries. This is one of the main problems adults encounter with adolescents (Mesch, 2006; Wolf, 2013). When the adolescent is gifted there is a tendency to let them decide about subjects that non-gifted adolescents usually are not allowed to decide upon. This tendency might be harmful both to the adolescent and to her or his parents, as being very smart does not necessarily mean being mature enough to be treated as an adult, and without parental authority the adolescent’s ability to conform to certain rules will not get enough practice. In addition, if the gifted adolescent has siblings it is the duty of the parents to give all of them the same opportunity to exhibit their maturity and offer advantages only upon good behavior and not because of a high cognitive level.

Depression, death ideation and death thoughts. Studies have shown that a high rate of adolescents think about suicide (Vander Stoep, 2009). In the US, suicide has been the third cause of death among adolescents (Anderson, 2002); there have been even many more suicide attempts and suicide thoughts (Center for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2006). Suicide has been found as the fourth leading cause of death among 12-year-olds (Hoyert et al., 2006). A study done in Washington public schools among 4447 students found that 11% of eighth graders had considered attempting suicide in the prior year (Washington State Department of Health [DOH], 2007). High rates of depression and suicide have been found elsewhere.

According to the World Health Organizations (2017), about 800,000 people die due to suicide every year, and suicide is the second leading cause of death among 15–29-year-olds. Depression is the third leading cause of illness and disability among adolescents, and suicide is the third leading cause of death in older adolescents (15–19 years) (Adolescents: health risks and solutions, 2017).

Death thoughts, suicide ideation and even suicide trials are closely connected to the age when the perception of death is mature enough (David, 2015). Because of the accelerated cognitive development of gifted children, it is important that depression among them will be identified as soon as possible, and if they speak about death – especially when they mention suicide – this must be taken into consideration and be treated even if they are just 8 years old, as quite often it happens that gifted children “think” like adolescents several years before they start the physiological, hormonal, or emotional changes normally observed among “regular” teenagers. When the gifted reach adolescence, studies show that the more vulnerable among them are at risk for suicide (Yewchuk & Jobagy, 2001).

Intensity and overexcitability. During adolescence there is usually intellectual, spiritual, social, physical and hormonal arousal (Mofield et al., 2015). Overexcitability, which is a typical characteristic of many gifted individuals (Ackerman, 1997, 2009; Almutairi, 2008; Bailey, 2011; Beach, 2005; Bouchard, 2004; Rinn et al., 2010; Tieso, 2007; Tolan, 1994), does not disappear during adolescence, and many a time become even more intense. Thus, gifted adolescents tend to be even more sensitive, aroused, intense and “touchy” than adolescents in general.

Inability to accept injustice or inequity and become pro-active in fighting against such phenomena. During adolescence social subjects, matters of fairness, justice, morality and equity become important to many adolescents (Bondü, & Elsner, 2015). These issues are of importance to many gifted children during childhood (Delaune, 2016; Roeper, & Silverman, 2009; Silverman, 1994; White, 2001), but their intensity increases with age and many gifted adolescents become more involved in activities, such as joining groups active in equality advancing, getting justice to minorities, fighting for animals’ rights, publishing materials about morality, and the like.

Spirituality tendency. Along with “looking for meaning” and “asking existential questions” many adolescents become interested in religion, whether the one they had been born to or to another, which seems more attractive; vegetarianism/veganism, pacifism and many other spiritual, social or moral issues that require complete dedication and changing one’s lifestyle. More than 100 years ago Hall (1904, p. 556) had mentioned that the Catholic Church had used the longing of the adolescent to the “spiritual” or “super-natural”. Gifted adolescents, who need a lot of excitement, who are sensitive to justice, inequality and suffer tend to the sublime even more than their “regular” peers (Coes, 1990; Frazer, 2011; Lovecky, 1998; Navan, 2012; Piechowski, 2003; Roeper, 2010; Tolan, 2007).

Perfectionism, blame, shame and self-criticism. Each of these personality traits or feelings tends to intensify during adolescence (Abd-El-Fattah, & Fakhroo, 2012; Damian et al., 2013; Esau et al., 2008; McArdle, & Duda, 2004; Roxborough et al., 2012; Soenens et al., 2008; Speirs Neumeister et al., 2009; Stoeber & Childs, 2011; Szentágotai-Táatar et al., 2015). Perfectionism and self-criticism are quite common among the gifted (Ablard, & Parker, 1997; Damian et al., 2017; Speirs Neumeister, 2004; Speirs Neumeister et al., 2009). According to Steinberg (2008b), the changes adolescents go through – intellectually, emotionally and

socially – make them more vulnerable to develop perfectionism. The same thing happened with self-awareness, self-image, self-efficacy, and self-esteem (Jain et al., 2013; Jimoh, & Oyerinde, 2013; Makewa, & Muthoni, 2015; Pajares, 2006; Sandu et al., 2015). Thus, the dealing with being gifted and going through these issues typical to adolescence puts gifted adolescents more at risk.

Self-discipline is a better predictor of future success than intelligence quotient (IQ) (Duckworth, & Seligman, 2005). However, during adolescence it becomes quite hard to educate towards it, or even recommend it, as self-discipline is usually perceived as rigidity, and being self-disciplined – as not being “cool” (Pickhardt, 2013). Materializing one’s giftedness in all areas requires a substantial amount of self-discipline, thus this contradiction, between age-matched conventions and giftedness “requirements” puts the gifted adolescent in an inconvenient situation where she or he must choose between society and one’s own needs.

Many adolescents get involved in *romantic relationships*; adolescence is, in fact, the time when it is expected to practice one’s abilities to maintain deeper connections with significant others (Collins, 2003; Furman & Shaffer, 2003; Furman, & Shomaker, 2008; Meier & Allen, 2009). But falling in love is risky because the person we love the most is capable of causing us to hurt the worst (Pickhardt, 2013). Gifted adolescents are at a greater risk than their peers because of their higher sensitivity level (Daniels, 2009; Daniels, & Piechowski, 2008; Daniels, & Meckstroth, 2008; Piechowski, 2006; Randell, 2016; Silverman, 1994; Silvers et al., 2012), and rejection from a significant other might cause them substantial harm (Hafen et al., 2014).

Inability, or at least *difficulty to accept “white lies” of half-truths*, as well as *injustice*. On the one hand, It is considered quite “acceptable” to lie to children, especially “for their own good”, namely, in order to “protect” them from truths that might be difficult to accept (Heyman et al., 2009). By adolescence a complex set of beliefs about the contexts in which lying is acceptable has usually been developed (Perkins & Turiel, 2007). Stability of *justice sensitivity* increases from childhood to early adolescence (Bondü & Elsner, 2015; Bondü & Krahé, 2015). Thus, the conflict of the gifted adolescent, who tends to be morally sensitive (Lovecky, 1997; Silverman, 1994), between the social or familial legitimacy of the use of “white lies” or “half-truths” and the inner conscious, which rebels against such behaviors, is increased. This might cause confrontations in school, at home and practically in all social interactions.

The difficulty to accept the “wisdom of the old”, to learn from “an experienced person” or from “someone who had been there”. Adolescents prefer, in most cases, to live their lives with as little as possible of parental guidance, instructions or demand (Rich-Harris, 2009). Thus, sentences such as “when I was your age” or “you should learn from MY experience” are usually rejected by them as irrelevant, even ridiculous. Gifted adolescents are in many cases more intelligent than their teachers, and sometimes even from their parents. Thus, they do not usually consider these adults as role models, or even people who should be respected

and obeyed to. The conflicts that arise because of this fact might accelerate and cause estrangement from these adults who are responsible for the physical and emotional well-being of these adolescents.

Many adolescents experience a period of *un-even growth, a flow of development*, acceleration of maturity in various kinds of activities – sports, music, writing, or any other artistic activity, or social accelerated urge manifested in voluntary work in organizations, such as Scouts, the Red Cross, or at refugee camps. While Hall (1904) was the first to describe this phenomenon, thousands of studies have been written in the 20th century about the outburst of creativity in all activities that is a typical characteristic of adolescence. The Milgram and Hong studies have shown that the gifted tend to have more hobbies and dedicate a greater part of their lives to extra-curricular activities (Hong & Milgram, 2008; Milgram, 2003; Milgram & Hong, 1999).

Thus, the conflict many adolescent experience – between high achievements in school and “doing my thing”, between getting high grades and satisfying their parent – sometimes themselves – and investigating more time in a hobby that makes them happy but is not necessarily connected to their professional horizon, is quite often intensified among the gifted. As gifted adolescents usually have many interests, many areas they want to dedicate themselves to – questions such as “shall I give up the piano for mathematics” have sometimes to be faced in the early teens, and the responsibility of choosing one area and giving up something that might contribute to one’s professional future is a heavy emotional load.

Sexual orientation is a main problem for the majority of adolescents who have not yet come to terms with their sexual preferences, namely, same-sex, other-sex or both. It is even a greater problem for those who feel they were not born in the “right” or “proper” gender, namely, the biological sex does not suit their gender identity, but unlike adults, cannot do anything about it yet. Many studies have been conducted about risk factors among gay adolescent or young adults (Higa et al., 2012; McDermott, 2014), but the sub-population of gay adolescents who are also gifted has been proven to be even at a higher risk, e.g. – for suicide ideation (Sedillo, 2013).

Summary

The description of problems typical to all adolescents and those who are intensified among gifted adolescents is but a beginning of a study that aims to focus on the special needs of the gifted adolescent, and by no means aims to include all of them. However, it gives a partial glimpse to the complicated, conflictual, intense and sometimes over-loaded life of the gifted teenager who is, in many cases, intellectually and cognitively more developed than most adults around him or her, but still must obey them – at home and in school. It shows how adolescents have to juggle among many tasks, many developmental phenomena and many social conventions and rules, and how this juggling might cause many legal, social and familial problems.

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